

RESEARCH ON THE LINGUOCULTUROLOGICAL RESEARCH OF THE
NAMES OF ARTISTIC WORKS

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Annotation:

In this article, the science of onomastics is divided into the following groups (departments) according to the categories of objects that have received famous names, a number of scientific directions have appeared in Uzbek linguistics, for example: experimental phonetics, phonology, morphonology, phraseology, stylistics (stylistics), speech culture, social linguistics (sociolinguistics), areal linguistics, linguostatistics etc. are discussed.

Key words: nicknames, cosmonymy, spatial space, galaxies, constellations, sociolinguistics

In the 60s and 70s of the 20th century, a number of scientific directions appeared in Uzbek linguistics. For example: experimental phonetics, phonology, morphonology, phraseology, stylistics (stylistics), speech culture, social linguistics (sociolinguistics), areal linguistics, linguostatistics, etc. Uzbek onomastics is also considered one of the new fields of linguistics that emerged in those times. It is known that onomastics is a branch of linguistics that studies all nouns, the history of their appearance and change, as well as the sum of all nouns in the language. The science of onomastics aims to identify and study existing onomastic systems in the language. The science of onomastics divides objects that have received famous names into the following groups (departments): anthroponymy - famous names of people (names, surnames, patronymics, nicknames, nicknames), toponymy - famous names of geographical objects, theonymy - various names of gods, goddesses, religious-mythical persons and creatures according to religious imaginations, zoonymy - nicknames given to animals, cosmonymy - regions of space, galaxies, constellations, etc. in scientific circulation and popular Astronomy is a set of names of some celestial bodies (planets and stars). In addition, there are several other divisions (groups) of onomastics. For example, one section of onomastics is called realonyms (names of objects that exist before and now), and

miphonems, which are opposite to it, mean the names of imaginary - physical objects. Researching famous names in literary texts is a special problem, which is the main task of artistic onomastics or onomapoetics. Onomastics also studies phonetic, morphological, derivational (formation, formation), semantic, etymological aspects of famous names using comparative-historical, structural, genetic, areal, onomastic mapping and other methods of linguistics. In this sense, in Uzbek linguistics, studying the expressive possibilities of language units in the national language, conducting scientific research in this field, and developing analytical methods and methodologies are among the most urgent issues. It is known that during the past period, a lot of work was done on the study of place names, Uzbek names and ethnonyms. The importance of scientific research in this field is increasing. The researches of scientists such as T. Nafasov, S. Qorayev, Z. Dosimov, B. Orinboyev, N. Okhunov, T. Ernazarov, H. Kholmo'minov, S. Naimov are a worthy contribution to the development of Uzbek onomastics. . The demonstrative part of nouns-language is the most paradoxical situations, the analysis of which should contribute to the emergence of new, deeper general linguistic concepts. Various features of famous names (nouns) in the language have been attracting the attention of scientists of various fields since ancient times. For example, in the works of ancient Greek scientists Aristotle, Democritus, and Heraclitus, opinions were expressed about the characteristics of famous names. For example, Aristotle considers the noun as one of the parts of speech in his work "Poetics" and defines it as follows: "A noun is a complex, meaningful word, which does not indicate time, and whose parts do not have meaning by themselves." Julius Pollux, who lived in the 1st century BC, created a dictionary explaining the nouns called "Onomastics". The Stoics, including Chrysippus, classified nouns as a separate language unit, a group of words. Famous nouns during the Renaissance and the Middle Ages (T. Hobbs, D. Locke, G. Leibniz) and throughout the XIX century (D. Mill, X. Joseph, etc.), their place in the lexical layer of the language the debate continued. The most important issue in this field was to determine the meaning of famous nouns. During the XVII-XIX centuries, this problem was studied not only by linguists, but also by philosophers and logicians. The great English logician John Stuart Mill (1806-1873) spent a lot of effort on studying this problem. According to his interpretation, proper nouns do not convey meaning, they help to know an object and distinguish it from other objects as unique signs and labels. The name of an object or a person (noun) cannot be a full basis for the description of that

object or person. Developing his thoughts, Dj. Mill divides words into two groups: a) words-signs, b) characterizing (connotative) words.

Uzbek onomastics or nomenclology emerged as a separate scientific direction in the 60s and 70s of the last century. Uzbek nomenclature has become one of the most developed fields since the second half of the last century. Especially in a number of areas such as anthroponymy, toponymy, ethnonymy, very fruitful work has been done in this field. For example, the materials of Uzbek names (anthroponyms) were collected extensively, four candidate theses (E. Begmatov - 1965, G'. Sattorov - 1990, S. Rahimov - 1998, R. Khudoyberganov - 2007) were defended, E. Begmatov's "Spelling of Personal Names" (1970), "Spelling of Uzbek Names" (1972), "Uzbek Names" (1991), "Meaning of Uzbek Names" (1998; 2004; 2010), " The books "The beauty of the name" (1994) were published. I.Mirzayev made some observations about giving personal names and geographical names in literary translation⁵.

However, in addition to general works within the field, separate scientific works dedicated to the names of artistic works have not yet been carried out in Uzbek linguistics. Various researches have been conducted on the toponyms and anthroponyms used only in the samples of artistic creations. In this field, a number of researches were conducted in Uzbek linguistics. We can say that the onomastic scope of the Uzbek language is an extremely complex and extensive concept. One of the urgent problems of Uzbek nomenclology is to carefully collect the material of nouns belonging to all macro-scale, micro-scale and scales of the Uzbek language, to study their nominative, motivational, and functional properties. Such a large-scale study is not only theoretical, but also of great practical importance for the field of onomastics

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